

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Strong Gamma Group

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Abstract

Objectives: The primary goal of this study is to present the concept of a strong Γ -group as a generalization of Γ -group. **Methods and Findings:** We have investigated some of the properties of the Γ -group and extended it to introduce the idea of a strong Γ -group. **Novelty:** Every strong Γ -group is a Γ -group, but not all Γ -groups are strong Γ -groups. Further if G is a non-empty Γ -semigroup and for all $a, b \in G$, the equations $a\alpha x = b$ and $y\alpha a = b$ for all $x, y \in G$ and for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$ have unique solutions in G , then G is a strong Γ -group. Also, we characterize that non-empty subset H of a strong Γ -group G is a strong Γ -subgroup if and only if for all $a, b \in H, a\alpha c \in H$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$ where c is strong inverse of b in G . Finally, we prove that the intersection of two strong Γ -subgroups is again a strong Γ -subgroup and the center of strong Γ -group $C(G)$ is also a Γ -subgroup.

Keywords: Semigroup; Strong Γ -group; Strong Γ -subgroup; Centre of Γ -group

1 Introduction

The notion of a ternary algebraic system was introduced by Lehmer in 1932. As a speculation of ring, the notion of a Γ -ring was introduced by N Nobusawa in 1964. In 1981, M. K. Sen introduced the notion of a Γ -semigroup as a generalization of semigroup. In 1995, Rao⁽¹⁾ introduced the notion of a Γ -semiring as a generalization of Γ ring. The formal study of semi groups begins in the early 20th century. Rao studied ideals of Γ -semirings, semirings, semigroups and Γ -semigroup. In this paper, we study the concept of a strong Γ -group as a generalization of Γ -group. Further, we prove some basic results regarding strong Γ -subgroup, centre of strong Γ -group etc. and study some fundamental properties of a strong Γ -group.

1.1 Preliminaries

We include some necessary preliminaries from⁽¹⁻³⁾ for the sake of completeness.

Definition 2.1. A semigroup is an algebraic system (G, \cdot) consisting of a non-empty set G together with an associative binary operation \cdot .

Definition 2.2. An algebraic system (G, \cdot) consisting of a non-empty set G together with an associative binary operation \cdot is called a group if it satisfies:

- (i) there exists $e \in G$ such that $x.e = e.x = x$ for all $x \in G$.
- (ii) if for each $x \in G$, there exists $y \in G$ such that $x.y = y.x = e$.

Definition 2.3. Let G and Γ be non-empty sets. Then we call G a Γ -semigroup if there exists a mapping $G \times \Gamma \times G \rightarrow G$, (images of (x, α, y) will be denoted by $x\alpha y$, $x, y \in G, \alpha \in \Gamma$) such that it satisfies $x\alpha(y\beta z) = (x\alpha y)\beta z$ for all $x, y, z \in G$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$.

Definition 2.4. A Γ -semigroup G is said to be commutative if $x\alpha y = y\alpha x$ for all $x, y \in G$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$.

Definition 2.5. Let G be a Γ -semigroup. An element $e \in G$ is said to be unity if for each $x \in G$, there exists $\alpha \in \Gamma$ such that $x\alpha e = e\alpha x = x$.

Definition 2.6. In a Γ -semigroup G with unity e , an element $x \in G$ is said to be left invertible (right invertible) if there exists $y \in G, \alpha \in \Gamma$ such that $y\alpha x = e$ ($x\alpha y = e$).

Definition 2.7. A Γ -semigroup G with unity e , an element $u \in G$ is said to be unit if there exists $v \in G$ and $\alpha \in \Gamma$ such that $u\alpha v = e = v\alpha u$.

Definition 2.8. A Γ -semigroup G with zero element 0 is said to hold cancellation laws if $x \neq 0, x\alpha y = x\alpha z, y\alpha x = z\alpha x$, where $x, y, z \in G, \alpha \in \Gamma$ then $y = z$.

Definition 2.9. A Γ -semigroup G is said to be Γ -group if it satisfies:

- (i) if there exists $e \in G$ and for each $x \in G$, there exists $\alpha \in \Gamma$ such that $x\alpha e = e\alpha x = x$.
- (ii) if for each element $x \neq 0$, there exists $y \in G, \alpha \in \Gamma$ such that $x\alpha y = y\alpha x = e$.

Remark 2.10. Every group G is a Γ -group if $\Gamma = G$ and ternary operation is $x\alpha y$ defined as the binary operation of the group. The unity of a Γ -group may not be unique.

Example 2.11. Let G and Γ be the set of all rational numbers and the set of all natural numbers respectively. Define the ternary operation $G \times \Gamma \times G \rightarrow G$ by $(x, \alpha, y) \rightarrow x\alpha y$ using the usual multiplication. Then G is a Γ -group.

Definition 2.12. An element x of a Γ -semigroup G is said to be a strong Γ -idempotent if $x\gamma x = x$ for all $\gamma \in \Gamma$.

Definition 2.13. A Γ -semigroup G is said to be strong Γ -idempotent if every element of G is strong Γ -idempotent.

Definition 2.14. Let G be a Γ -semigroup. An element $e \in G$ is said to be strong identity e if for each $x \in G$, we have $x\alpha e = e\alpha x = x$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$.

Definition 2.15. Let G be a Γ -semigroup with strong identity $e \in G$. An element $x \in G$ is said to have strong inverse in G if there exists $y \in G$ such that $x\alpha y = y\alpha x = e$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$.

Definition 2.16. A Γ -semigroup G is said to be a strong Γ -group if it satisfies:

- (i) if G has strong identity $e \in G$;
- (ii) And every element of G has strong inverse in G .

Example 2.17. Let G be the set of all positive rational numbers and Γ be the set of all real numbers whose square is 1. Define the ternary operation $G \times \Gamma \times G \rightarrow G$ by $(x, \alpha, y) \rightarrow x \cdot |\alpha| \cdot y$, where \cdot is the usual multiplication. Then G is a strong Γ -group.

Example 2.18. Let G be a set of real solutions of the equation $x^2 = x$ and let Γ be the set of all non-positive integers. Define the ternary operation $G \times \Gamma \times G \rightarrow G$ by $(x, \alpha, y) \rightarrow \text{Max}(x, y, \alpha)$, where \cdot is the usual multiplication. Then G is a strong Γ -group.

Example 2.19. Let G be the set of all non-zero real numbers and let $\Gamma = \{2\pi ki : k \in \mathbb{N}\}$.

Define the ternary operation $G \times \Gamma \times G \rightarrow G$ by $(x, \alpha, y) \rightarrow x \cdot e^{\alpha} \cdot y$, where \cdot is the usual multiplication. Then G is a strong Γ -group.

2 Main Results

Theorem 3.1. Every strong Γ -group is a Γ -group.

Proof. Let G be a strong Γ -group. Then G is a Γ -semigroup with strong identity $e \in G$ and every element $a \in G$ has a strong inverse in G . This implies that for all $x \in G, \alpha \in \Gamma, x\alpha e = e\alpha x = x$ and for all $x \neq 0$ there exists $y \in G$ such that $x\alpha y = y\alpha x = e$.

Note: - Every Γ -group need not be a strong Γ -group.

Example 3.2. Let G and Γ be the set of all rational numbers and the set of all natural numbers respectively. Define the ternary operation $G \times \Gamma \times G \rightarrow G$ by $(x, \alpha, y) \rightarrow x\alpha y$, where \cdot is the usual multiplication. Then G is a Γ -group. Let e be the strong identity of G . Then for each $x \neq 0 \in G, x = x\alpha e = e\alpha x$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. This implies that $e = 1/\alpha$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$ and hence e depends on α which is not possible. Thus, G does not have a strong identity. Therefore, G is not a strong Γ -group.

Theorem 3.3. (Cancellation Laws) Let G be a strong Γ -group. If $x\alpha y = x\alpha z$, $y\beta x = z\beta x$, where $x, y, z \in G$ and for all $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$ then $y = z$.

Proof. Let $x, y, z \in G$ and $\alpha, \gamma \in \Gamma$. Suppose e is the strong identity of G . Then $x\alpha(e\gamma y) = x\alpha(e\gamma z)$ implies that $(x\alpha e)\gamma y = (x\alpha e)\gamma z$. Now $x\alpha e \in G$, there exists $w \in G$ such that $(x\alpha e)\delta w = w\delta(x\alpha e) = e$ for all $\delta \in \Gamma$. Therefore $y = e\eta y = w\delta(x\alpha e)\eta y = w\delta(x\alpha(e\eta y)) = w\delta(x\alpha(e\eta z)) = w\delta(x\alpha e)\eta z = e\eta z = z$ for all $\eta \in \Gamma$. Similarly $y\beta x = z\beta x$ implies $y = z$.

Theorem 3.4. The strong identity of a strong Γ -group is unique.

Proof. If possible, let e_1, e_2 be two strong identities of a strong Γ -group G . Therefore, $e_1\alpha e_2 = e_1$ and $e_1\alpha e_2 = e_2$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. Hence, $e_1 = e_2$.

Theorem 3.5. The strong inverse of each element of a strong Γ -group is unique.

Proof. Let e be the strong identity of a strong Γ -group G and $a \in G$ be an arbitrary element. If possible, let $b_1, b_2 \in G$ be two strong inverses of a . Therefore, $a\alpha b_1 = e = b_1\alpha a$ and $a\beta b_2 = e = b_2\beta a$ for all $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$. Now $b_1 = b_1\alpha e = b_1\alpha(a\beta b_2) = (b_1\alpha a)\beta b_2 = e\beta b_2 = b_2$.

Theorem 3.6. Let G be a strong Γ -group. Then left strong identity and right strong identity are the same in G .

Proof. Let e_1 and e_2 be the left and right strong identities of G . Then $e_1\alpha x = x$ and $x\alpha e_2 = x$ for all $x \in G, \alpha \in \Gamma$. Now by taking $x = e_2$ and $x = e_1$ respectively in above relations, we have $e_1 = e_2$.

Theorem 3.7. Let G be a strong Γ -group. Then left strong inverse and right strong inverse of every element in a strong Γ -group is same.

Proof. Let e be the strong identity of G and b, c be the left and right strong inverses of an element $\in G$. Then $b\alpha a = e$ and $a\beta c = e$ for all $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$. Hence, $b = b\alpha e = b\alpha(a\beta c) = (b\alpha a)\beta c = e\beta c = c$.

Theorem 3.8. Let G be a strong Γ -group. Then the equations $a\alpha x = b$ and $y\alpha a = b$ have unique solutions in G for $a, b \in G, \alpha \in \Gamma$.

Proof. Let $a \in G$, therefore there exists $c \in G$ such that $a\alpha c = c\alpha a = e$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$ where e is the strong identity of G . Take $x = c\alpha b$, then $x \in G$. Now $a\alpha x = a\alpha(c\beta b) = (a\alpha c)\beta b = e\beta b = b$ for all $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$. Similarly, the solution of $y\alpha a = b$ exists. Further suppose that x_1 and x_2 are two solutions of the equation $a\alpha x = b$ in G . Therefore $a\alpha x_1 = b$ and $a\alpha x_2 = b$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. This implies that $a\alpha x_1 = a\alpha x_2$. By left cancellation law $x_1 = x_2$. Hence the equation $a\alpha x = b$ has a unique solution in G . By similar arguments one can prove that the equation $y\alpha a = b$ also has a unique solution in G .

Theorem 3.9. Let G be a non-empty Γ -semigroup. If for all $a, b \in G$, the equations $a\alpha x = b$ and $y\alpha a = b, \alpha \in \Gamma$ have solutions in G then G is a strong Γ -group.

Proof. For any $a, b \in G$, let the equations $a\alpha x = b$ and $y\alpha a = b, \alpha \in \Gamma$ have a solution in G . Since G is non empty, so there exists $a_0 \in G$. Therefore, the equations $a_0\alpha x = a_0$ and $y\alpha a_0 = a_0, \alpha \in \Gamma$ have solutions in G . Let $x = g$ and $y = f$ be the respective solutions of these equations in G . Thus $g, f \in G$ and $a_0\alpha g = a_0$ and $f\alpha a_0 = a_0$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. Now let $b \in G$ arbitrarily then there exist $x_0, y_0 \in G$ such that $a_0\alpha x_0 = b$ and $y_0\alpha a_0 = b$. By associativity of Γ -semigroup G , we have $b\beta g = (y_0\alpha a_0)\beta g = y_0\alpha(a_0\beta g) = y_0\alpha a_0 = b$. Also $f\beta b = f\beta(a_0\alpha x_0) = (f\beta a_0)\alpha x_0 = a_0\alpha x_0 = b$. Therefore $b\beta g = b$ and $f\beta b = b$ for all $b \in G$ and for all $\beta \in \Gamma$. Taking $b = f$ in $b\beta g = b$. This implies that $f\beta g = f$ and by taking $b = g$ in $f\beta b = b$, we have $f\beta g = g$. Thus $g = f$ for all $\beta \in \Gamma$. Putting $g = f$ in $b\beta g = b$ and $f\beta b = b$ for all $b \in G$ for all $\beta \in \Gamma$, we have $b\beta g = b$ and $g\beta b = b$ for all $b \in G, \beta \in \Gamma$. Thus g is the strong identity of G . Again, the equations $a\alpha x = g$ and $y\alpha a = g$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$ have solutions in G . Let $x = c$ and $y = d$ be their respective solutions in G . Therefore $a\alpha c = g$ and $d\alpha a = g$. Now $d = d\alpha g = d\alpha(a\alpha c) = (d\alpha a)\alpha c = g\alpha c = c$. Hence $a\alpha c = g$ and $c\alpha a = g$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$ implies that c is strong inverse of a for all $a \in G$. Thus, G is a strong Γ -group.

Theorem 3.10. Let G be a strong Γ -group. Then $x \in G$ is strong Γ -idempotent if and only if $x = e$, where e is strong identity of G .

Proof. Suppose $x \in G$ is strong Γ -idempotent, then $x\alpha x = x$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. Now $x\alpha x = e\alpha x$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. By right cancellation law we have $x = e$. Conversely, assume that $x = e$, then $x\alpha x = e\alpha e = e = x$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$.

Theorem 3.11. (Reversal Law) Let G be a strong Γ -group. Then for $x, y \in G$ and $\alpha \in \Gamma$, strong inverse of $x\alpha y$ is $z\beta w$ for all $\beta \in \Gamma$, where w and z are strong inverses of x and y respectively.

Proof. Let $x, y \in G$ and let w and z be strong inverses of x and y respectively.

Then for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \in \Gamma$, $(x\alpha y)\gamma(z\beta w) = x\alpha(y\gamma z)\beta w = x\alpha(e\beta w) = x\alpha w = e$. Also $(z\beta w)\delta(x\alpha y) = z\beta(w\delta x)\alpha y = z\beta(e\alpha y) = z\beta y = e$, where e is strong identity of G . This implies that strong inverse of $x\alpha y$ is $z\beta w$.

Definition 3.12. (Strong Γ -subgroup) A non-empty subset H of a strong Γ -group G is said to be a strong Γ -subgroup of G if H itself is a strong Γ -group.

Theorem 3.13. The strong identity of a strong Γ -group and strong Γ -subgroup are same.

Proof. Let G be a strong Γ -group and H be its strong Γ -subgroup. Let e and e' be the strong identities of G and H respectively. Suppose $a \in H$ is any element, then $a\alpha e' = e' \alpha a = a$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. Since $a \in H$ and $H \subset G$, so $a \in G$. Thus $a\alpha e = e\alpha a = a$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. Therefore $a\alpha e = a\alpha e'$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. So, by left cancellation law $e = e'$.

Theorem 3.14. The strong inverse of any element of a strong Γ -subgroup H is same as the strong inverse of the element regarded as the element of the strong Γ -group G .

Proof. Let e be the strong identity of G and H . Since $H \subset G$, so for $a \in H$ we have $a \in G$. Let b be strong inverse of a in H and c be the strong inverse of a in G . This implies that $b\alpha a = e$ and $c\alpha a = e$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. Thus $b\alpha a = c\alpha a$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. So, by right cancellation law $b = c$.

Theorem 3.15. A non-empty subset H of a strong Γ -group G is a strong Γ -subgroup if and only if

(i) $a\alpha b \in H$ for all $a, b \in H$ and for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$.

(ii) for all $a \in H$ there exists $b \in H$ such that $a\alpha b = e$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$, where e is strong identity of G .

Proof. Suppose H is a strong Γ -subgroup. Then H is a strong Γ -group under the same ternary operation as that of G . Thus (i) and (ii) hold. Conversely, assume that (i) and (ii) hold in H . Since G is a strong Γ -group and $H \subset G$, so $x\alpha(y\beta z) = (x\alpha y)\beta z$ for all $x, y, z \in H$ and for all $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$. Again $H \neq \emptyset$, by (ii) for $a \in H$ there exists $b \in H$ such that $a\alpha b = e$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. Thus (i) implies, $e = a\alpha b \in H$.

Theorem 3.16. A non-empty subset H of a strong Γ -group G is a strong Γ -subgroup if and only if for all $a, b \in H$ and for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$ implies $a\alpha c \in H$ where c is strong inverse of b in G .

Proof. Suppose H is a non-empty strong Γ -subgroup of a strong Γ -group G . Then H is a strong Γ -group under the same ternary operation as that of G . Therefore, for all $a, b \in H$ and for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$, $a\alpha c \in H$, where c is strong inverse of b in G . Conversely, since G is a strong Γ -group and $H \subset G$, $x\alpha(y\beta z) = (x\alpha y)\beta z$ for all $x, y, z \in H$ and for all $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$. Let $a \in H$ be any arbitrary element. Then for $a \in H$ and for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$ implies $a\alpha b \in H$, where b is strong inverse of a (i.e. $a\alpha b = b\alpha a = e$, where e is strong identity of G). Thus $e \in H$. Since $H \neq \emptyset$, So let $a \in H$. This implies that for $e, a \in H$, $e\alpha b \in H$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$ and $b = b\beta e = e\beta b \in H$ for all $\beta \in \Gamma$ where b is strong inverse of a . Hence H is a strong Γ -subgroup.

Theorem 3.17. Intersection of two strong Γ -subgroups is again a strong Γ -subgroup of the strong Γ -group.

Proof. Let H_1 and H_2 be two strong Γ -subgroups of a strong Γ -group G . Since $e \in H_1 \cap H_2$ so $H_1 \cap H_2 \neq \emptyset$, where e is the strong identity of strong Γ -group G . Let $x, y \in H_1 \cap H_2$. This implies that $x, y \in H_1$ and $x, y \in H_2$. Therefore $x\alpha z \in H_1$ and $x\alpha z \in H_2$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$, where z is strong inverse of y in G (since H_1 and H_2 are two strong Γ -subgroups). Hence $x\alpha z \in H_1 \cap H_2$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$.

Definition 3.18. (Center of a strong Γ -group) Let G be a strong Γ -group then Center of a strong Γ -group G is a subset of G consisting of all elements x of G such that $x\alpha y = y\alpha x$ for all $y \in G$ and for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. It is denoted by $C(G)$.

Theorem 3.19. Let G be a strong Γ -group. Then the Centre $C(G)$ of G is a strong Γ -subgroup of G .

Proof. Let e be the strong identity of G , then $e\alpha x = x\alpha e$ for all $x \in G$ and for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. Therefore $e \in C(G)$, so $C(G) \neq \emptyset$. Let $g_1, g_2 \in C(G)$ then $g_1\alpha y = y\alpha g_1$ and $g_2\alpha y = y\alpha g_2$ for all $y \in G$ and for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. Since $g_2 \in G$, there exists strong inverse $g_3 \in G$ such that $g_2\alpha g_3 = g_3\alpha g_2 = e$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. Now $g_3\alpha y = g_3\alpha(y\alpha e) = g_3\alpha(y\alpha(g_2\alpha g_3)) = g_3\alpha((y\alpha g_2)\alpha g_3) = g_3\alpha((g_2\alpha y)\alpha g_3) = ((g_3\alpha g_2)\alpha y)\alpha g_3 = (e\alpha y)\alpha g_3 = y\alpha g_3$ for all $y \in G$. Therefore, $g_3 \in C(G)$. Thus $y\alpha(g_1\alpha g_3) = (y\alpha g_1)\alpha g_3 = (g_1\alpha y)\alpha g_3 = g_1\alpha(y\alpha g_3) = g_1\alpha(g_3\alpha y) = (g_1\alpha g_3)\alpha y$ for all $y \in G$ and for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. Therefore $g_1\alpha g_3 \in C(G)$ and hence $C(G)$ is a strong Γ -subgroup G .

Theorem 3.20. Let G be a strong Γ -group. Then G is a commutative strong Γ -group if and only if $C(G) = G$.

Proof. Let G be commutative strong Γ -group. Then for $x \in G$, $x\alpha y = y\alpha x$ for all $y \in G$ and for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. Therefore, $x \in C(G)$ and thus $G \subset C(G)$. Clearly $C(G) \subset G$ being a strong Γ -subgroup of G . Conversely, let $x, y \in G$. Since $C(G) = G$, then $x, y \in C(G)$ and hence $x\alpha y = y\alpha x$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. This implies that G is commutative strong Γ -group.

Definition 3.21. (Normalizer of an element of a strong Γ -group) Let G be a strong Γ -group, then Normalizer of an element a of G is a subset of G consisting of all elements x of G such that $x\alpha a = a\alpha x$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. It is denoted by $N(a)$.

Theorem 3.22. Let G be a strong Γ -group, then normalizer $N(a)$ is a strong Γ -subgroup of G .

Proof. Let e be the strong identity of G , then $e\alpha x = x\alpha e$ for all $x \in G$ and for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. In particular $e\alpha a = a\alpha e$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. Therefore $e \in N(a)$, so $N(a) \neq \emptyset$. Let $g_1, g_2 \in N(a)$, then $g_1\alpha a = a\alpha g_1$ and $g_2\alpha a = a\alpha g_2$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. Since $g_2 \in G$, there exists $g_3 \in G$ such that $g_2\alpha g_3 = g_3\alpha g_2 = e$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. Now $g_3\alpha a = g_3\alpha(a\alpha e) = g_3\alpha(a\alpha(g_2\alpha g_3)) = g_3\alpha((a\alpha g_2)\alpha g_3) = g_3\alpha((g_2\alpha a)\alpha g_3) = ((g_3\alpha g_2)\alpha a)\alpha g_3 = (e\alpha a)\alpha g_3 = a\alpha g_3$. Therefore $g_3 \in N(a)$. Now $a\alpha(g_1\alpha g_3) = (a\alpha g_1)\alpha g_3 = (g_1\alpha a)\alpha g_3 = g_1\alpha(a\alpha g_3) = g_1\alpha(g_3\alpha a) = (g_1\alpha g_3)\alpha a$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. Thus $g_1\alpha g_3 \in N(a)$. Hence, $N(a)$ is a strong Γ -subgroup of G .

Theorem 3.23. Let G be a strong Γ -group. Then G is commutative strong Γ -group if and only if $N(a) = G$ for all $a \in G$.

Proof. Let G be commutative strong Γ – group. Then for $x \in G$, we have $x\alpha y = y\alpha x$ for all $y \in G$ and for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. In particular $x\alpha a = a\alpha x$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. Therefore $x \in N(a)$ and thus $G \subset N(a)$. Clearly $N(a) \subset G$ being a strong Γ – subgroup of G . Conversely, let $x, y \in G$. Since $N(a) = G$ for all $a \in G$, then in particular $N(x) = N(y)$. Therefore, $x\alpha y = y\alpha x$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. This implies that G is commutative strong Γ – group.

3 Conclusion

This article presents the idea of a strong Γ – group and provides some key findings in this area. We pay particular attention to outcomes that hold true for strong Γ – groups but not for Γ – groups. For researchers, this article has a lot of potential.

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